

D1.3 – Concept descriptions of user interfaces and human-robot interaction – Final

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Abstract

The first version of Deliverable 1.3 "Concept descriptions of user interfaces and human-robot interaction", is to be updated after each development sprint (at M13, M18; and M24). This present, the final version, presents the basics of the general UI concept; being almost unaltered, it has minor updates from the previous versions of the D1.3. However, this deliverable also describes how the two user interfaces introduced in the final version, BIM@Construction and BIM@SiteOffice, have been evaluated in user test, along with reporting the method, results and conclusions. Finally, the more detailed UI concepts of BIM@Emergency and BIM@AnyWhere has been introduced.

Keywords

Building Information Modelling, Digital Twin, User interface concepts, Usability, User Experience, Extended reality, Virtual reality, Augmented reality, Mixed reality, Human-Robot interaction

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Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Meaning
AR	Augmented Reality
BIM	Building Information Modelling
FOV	Field of View
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HMD	Head Mounted Display
HRI	Human-Robot interaction
HVAC	Heating, ventilation, and air conditioning
MR	Mixed Reality
MUVR	Multi-User-Virtual-Reality
SSQ	Simulator Sickness Questionnaire
SUS	System Usability Scale
UI	User Interface
UX	User Experience
VR	Virtual Reality
XR	extended Reality

BIMprove project

In the past 20 years, productivity in the European construction industry has increased by 1% annually only, which is at the lower end compared to other industrial sectors. Consequently, the sector has to step up its digitization efforts significantly, on the one hand to increase its competitiveness and on the other hand to get rid of its image as dirty, dangerous and physical demanding working environment. Construction industry clearly needs to progress beyond Building Information Modelling when it comes to digitizing their processes in such a way that all stakeholders involved in the construction process can be involved.

The true potential of comprehensive digitization in construction can only be exploited if the current status of the construction work is digitally integrated in a common workflow. A Digital Twin provides construction companies with real-time data on the development of their assets, devices and products during creation and also enables predictions on workforce, material and costs.

BIMprove facilitates such a comprehensive end-to-end digital thread using autonomous tracking systems to continuously identify deviations and update the Digital Twin accordingly. In addition, locations of construction site personnel are tracked anonymously, so that **BIMprove** system services are able to optimize the allocation of resources, the flow of people and the safety of the employees. Information will be easily accessible for all user groups by providing personalized interfaces, such as wearable devices for alerts or VR visualizations for site managers. **BIMprove** is a cloud-based service-oriented system that has a multi-layered structure and enables extensions to be added at any time.

The main goals of **BIMprove** are a significant reduction in costs, better use of resources and fewer accidents on construction sites. By providing a complete digital workflow, BIMprove will help to sustainably improve the productivity and image of the European construction industry.

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1. Introduction

This deliverable is the final version of the deliverable D1.3. Deliverable has been updated after each development sprint (at M13, M18; and M24) In the first version of D1.3, general concepts and guidelines for studying technology and the related user interface were provided as background information to future studies. General user interface (UI) concept was described as well as BIM user interface categories. Two categories were described in more detail, namely the ones of BIM@SiteOffice and BIM@Construction. The second version describes the evaluation of the two earlier mentioned user interfaces. It also describes detailed UI concepts of BIM@Vehicle and BIM@OffSiteOffice.

This deliverable, the final version, presents the basics of the general UI concept, mainly being unaltered, it has minor updates from the previous versions of the D1.3. However, this deliverable also describes how the two user interfaces, BIM@Construction and BIM@SiteOffice, have been evaluated in user test, along with reporting the method, results and conclusions. Finally, the new more detailed UI concepts of BIM@Emergency and BIM@AnyWhere has been introduced.

2. Overview of General UI concept

2.1. Overview

The construction Digital Twin Model has various layers and users with different needs and requests for information. There is no ‘one-fit-for-all’ graphical user interface (GUI) for all user roles and needs. BIMprove’s general UI concept was been created based on user stories from deliverable 1.1 "Overall system design", requirements from deliverable 1.2. “Requirements list of BIMprove”, and expert evaluation to fulfil the most of user needs. The general UI concept can be seen in Figure 1. The UI concept has four modes:

1. Digital Twin
2. Immersive Digital Twin
3. Mobile
4. Notification and Warnings.

User is able to change modes based on device features and user profile-based access rights (see Figure 1). User can have the 1st person or 3rd person view in Immersive Digital Twin and Mobile modes. In the 1st person view, user will see information from digital twin in real scale, e.g., can feel as if being located in a real room in Virtual Reality. In the 3rd person view, user can see information from digital twin in free distance, e.g., zoom in and out in a 2D map. There are mini maps on the 1st person or 3rd person views, which supports user’s orientation on the BIMprove Digital Twin model and gives better situation awareness. The most urgent and relevant information will be given to user via Notification and Warning mode.

Figure 1. The general-level UI concept of BIMprove, to be used in various devices.

2.2. Modes

Digital Twin Mode

The main purpose of Digital Twin Mode is to modify and insert data to BIMprove Digital Twin. This mode is mainly based on existing BIM software, e.g., BIMsync. The Digital Twin Mode allows the user to explore the model from the 3rd person view and access meta-data based on access rights defined in the user profile.

Main device to have Digital Twin Mode is personal computer, e.g., laptop or workstation.

Immersive Digital Twin Mode

The main purpose of Digital Twin Mode is to show user BIMprove Digital Twin model in as realistic and detailed format as possible. With this mode, user is able to jump in to BIMprove Digital Twin and experience the environment in one-to-one scale by using high-end XR devices. This viewpoint is called the 1st person view. In the 3rd person view, user is able to experience BIMprove Digital Twin model from free distance by zooming in and out. The mini map is supporting user to orient him/herself in the 1st and 3rd person views, which supports better situation awareness.

Main device will be high-end eXtended Reality (XR) devices e.g. Big screen, Powerwall or VR/MR/AR headsets.

Mobile Mode

The main purpose of Mobile Mode is to show user BIMprove Digital Twin model as suitable format as possible with handheld devices. This mode is a simplified version of Immersive Digital Twin mode. User still has possibilities to switch between the 1st and 3rd person views, but the level of information is more limited. Main focus of Mobile mode is to provide user the most relevant BIMprove Digital Twin information based on his/her user profile and locations. This gives easy access to information and gives better situation awareness when being, e.g., on-site.

Main device will be mobile devices, that is, tablet and smart phone.

Notification and Warnings Mode

The main purpose of Notification and Warnings Mode is to inform user about the most urgent and relevant information without any delays. System will be based on most common notification functions which are natively supported in smartwatches and mobile phones. These functions are vibration,

sound and notification texts. Notifications and warning will be triggered based on BIMprove digital twin data and/or user location in construction site.

Main device will be handheld and wearable devices, e.g., smartwatch and mobile phone.

2.3. BIM@ Categories

In addition to the four modes of use described above, another way of categorising the BIMprove UIs is to apply the *context* of use. This is useful because of the heterogeneity of these contexts and thus the heterogeneity of the UIs themselves. There are six such categories in BIMprove (Aust et al., 2021), described briefly below.

BIM@Construction

First functional prototypes of BIM@Construction UIs have already been implemented. It supports immersive and mobile AR features on the construction site, for example to make future installations visible or installations “hidden” inside a wall.

BIM@Vehicle

This category covers the use of BIMprove from a vehicle. This, for example, could be a truck driver navigating the construction site or a crane operator checking the current 3D-model.

BIM@Emergency

One of the BIMprove-project's major goals is to improve both the avoidance of and the reaction to emergency situations. The BIM@Emergency category encompasses UIs to support both these goals. Possible user roles in this category are personnel of the construction company such as health and safety specialists, and emergency professionals, such as fire fighters and paramedics.

BIM@OffSiteOffice

To maintain the digital twin of the construction as the single source of truth throughout the construction process, the BIMprove-System needs to make it possible for planner engineers to make changes to their plans, when requested. This they will be able to do from their own offices.

BIM@Anywhere

BIMprove will be a cloud-based system. This UI category facilitates accessing building related data from anywhere via a mobile device. The difference to other categories of UIs, where the expected main devices will also be smartphones and tablets, are the user roles and the tasks.

BIM@SiteOffice

Aust et al. (2020) introduce "...the idea of a multi-user, multi-device XR-system to be set up at a construction site, for both co-located and remote use". This UI category comprises both, the context of using the BIMprove-

System from the construction site office and joining a multi-user-session from another office, the construction site itself, or from anywhere via mobile device.

3. User test

User tests were conducted for final evaluation of BIM@Construction and BIM@SiteOffice. Also, user feedback to BIMprove’s general UI concept (see sec 1.) was collected.

The test for BIM@SiteOffice was organised with real end-users in VIAS construction site in Madrid, Spain and HRS construction site in Lausanne, Switzerland.

The test for BIM@Construction was organised with real end-users in HRS construction site in Lausanne, Switzerland.

3.1. BIM@Construction User Tests

The user tests for BIM@Construction were conducted in HRS construction site in Lausanne, Switzerland in November 24, 2022. More specifically, the test space was a basement room of an apartment house under construction. The test system and space were set up during the previous day. The goal of the tests was to collect feedback from actual construction site personnel in the final phase of the development.

Altogether five (5) HRS employees participated in the tests, all of them representing the supervisor or manager level. The test persons performed the test individually. The tests were prepared, instructed and guided by researchers from VTT (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. Example of user tests. Person is testing BIM@Construction and HF expert is guiding the test and observing.

Procedure for the tests was as follows:

Duration: 1 hour

- Introduction
 - Test goals and methods
 - HoloLens training for the test user (utilising training mode in HoloLens)
 - Video for orientation, presenting the main functionalities of the AR-system
- Test performance with BIM@Construction AR-system
- SUS (System Usability Scale) questionnaire
- Interview

3.1.1. Use case

BIM@Construction can be viewed in first-person mode, that is, in the **immersive mode** (see Figure 3), in which the viewer is as if inside the building. User can do various tasks inside the building, both by deciding what details to see and also by adding more information to the building with digital means. It can also be perceived in the **third-person mode**, as if outside the building, so that the user can rotate the building model, look at it closer or further as needed (D1.3, v2).

Figure 3. Immersive mode. Left: Checking piping. Right: Using measurement tool.

During the actual test performance, the users wore HoloLens glasses and performed tasks in the basement room following the instructions from the test supervisor. The following tasks were given to the test user to perform with the BIM@Construction AR-system:

Immersive mode:

Options

- Show menu on palm, left hand
- Choose OPTIONS
 - Turn Follow me ON/OFF
- Change layers on/off and check layers (architectural, hydraulics...)
 - Walk and look around the room

- Look if pipes and holes on the wall and so on are in correct position. Look for anything that is interesting to you.
- Change opacity of architectural and ventilation (etc.)

Tools

- Choose TOOLS (from menu on palm)
- Measure width of the doorway
- Add any symbol: Question mark, cross mark, check mark

Floor plan

- Choose FLOORPLAN
- Zoom in / out floorplan

3rd person mode:

- Jump to 3rd person mode, turn off Immersive mode (below)
- Rotate / zoom the visible model of the building

3.1.2. Method

Both quantitative and qualitative methods for data collection were used in the test. Firstly, the test participants filled in System Usability Scale (SUS) questionnaire. The SUS scores calculated from individual questionnaires represent the system usability. SUS yields a single number representing a composite measure of the overall usability of the system being studied. Scores for individual questionnaire items are not meaningful on their own (Brooke, 1996). SUS scores have a range of 0 to 100. The users filled in the SUS questionnaire immediately after the test performance.

Secondly, semi-structured interviews were conducted with each participants after they had filled in the SUS questionnaire. The interview consisted of themes related to human-technology interaction and following the test procedure. The main focus was on user experience, usability and usefulness of the system.

Additionally, the test performances were observed by the researchers responsible for the test.

3.1.3. Results

System Usability Scale SUS

According to validation studies (Bangor et al., 2009; Brooke, 2013), the SUS score starting from 68-70 represents the level of acceptable system usability. Furthermore, the suggested acceptability ranges are: 0-50 not acceptable; 50-70 marginal; 70- acceptable.

SUS scores:

Test participant	SUS score
1	90
2	73
3	83
4	43
5	83

SUS score average: 74

Based on the SUS score average (74), the system usability was evaluated as acceptable. All expect one of the individual test participants evaluated the usability as acceptable, and three of the users gave a score over 80, which indicates very good usability. It should be noted that the result does not provide statistical significance due to low number of test participants.

As one user gave a score less than 50, meaning that usability is not on acceptable level, this should be further elaborated. The score was not at all in line with the rest of the scores. It should be noted that the particular user suffered from simulator sickness symptoms during and after the test. Secondly, minor issues in the beginning of the test caused some delay and time pressure in the schedule, and because of that, the user did not go through the HoloLens training mode, which all the other users did. These reasons might had affected the SUS evaluation, but it cannot be confirmed. During the actual test, the user had slightly more difficulties manipulating the objects than the other users. The interview results did not reveal any major or critical dissatisfaction towards the system usability, but the experienced usability issues were mainly seen as a matter of practice. This viewpoint should be taken into consideration still, since SUS also measures system learnability.

Interviews

“I’m really positive about this, I’m sure that this is going to be the future.” (Interviewee comment)

General system user experience

In the beginning of the interviews, the test participants were asked to use 2-3 words (adjectives) to describe their experience with the system based on their immediate impression. The following positive and negative expressions were used:

Positive expressions about the system (13)	Negative expressions about the system (1)
Interesting (2 times) Powerful (2 times) Interactive User friendly Impressive Visionary Easy to use Natural feeling Innovative Amazing Intuitive	Awkward

The system was generally experienced as very positive, since only one negative expression emerged from the participants. Some users felt the use of the system as surprisingly good and effective, as the expressions such as “amazing”, “impressive”, “powerful” and “visionary” demonstrate. The system was seen to bring real added value to work and it was mainly considered easy to use. The only negative expression (awkward) was a result of some simulator or motion sickness symptoms, which were reported by one user after the test.

The following sub-chapters provide more detailed information from the interviews.

Immersive (1st person) mode

The immersive mode was generally seen as the most important and useful feature of the system. This mode with AR visualization would help the user to see immediately if something is wrong between model and reality. It shows effectively what is built and what was planned to be built. This feature was experienced to be useful in everyday work on site. The users were generally satisfied with the visualization of different elements and accuracy provided by the system. Commercial viewpoint was also mentioned: The system can be used to demonstrate plans for the customer effectively.

In the immersive mode, the users also tested virtual tools provided by the system, such as virtual measuring tape, and symbols to be placed in virtual space (question and exclamation mark etc.). Floor plan of the building was also included in the system features and test tasks.

- *Measuring tape* as such is an important tool for the users, but the accuracy of the virtual tool was not sufficient in this system version, thus traditional, manual measurement tape is better according to users. The idea of virtual tool can still be considered.
- It was seen as important and useful that the system makes it possible to place a *virtual symbol* or note with comments in a specific place, so that other users can also see it. This improves communication with other people. It was suggested that the symbols placed in specific locations should be somehow synchronized with other systems as well.
- The usefulness of the virtual *floor plan* as such was not very obvious for the users. It was suggested that it could be improved if it would show the location of the user and other people, and for example symbols or notes placed in certain locations as well.

3rd person mode

The 3rd person mode with possibility to look and manipulate the model “from outside” was mainly seen as an interesting feature, but its benefit to work was not so obvious compared with the immersive mode. The 3rd person mode would probably not be that useful when user is on site, since the experienced advantage of AR is that person can go into construction site and see relevant things there immediately in immersive mode. In off-site work, the 3rd person mode can be however useful for communicating with other people, as looking at the whole model together can increase mutual understanding. The current AR-system with HoloLens cannot be used simultaneously by multiple users, thus other solutions should be considered. It was also mentioned, that 3rd person mode could help to see for example all the work tasks that are currently active.

User interface menus and interaction

The different features and functionalities of the system are operated through virtual, movable menus with buttons and switches, based on the features offered by HoloLens. Hand gestures are used for interaction with the menus. The usability of the virtual menus was considered mainly as quite good, simple and logical. Especially, the left hand palm menu (with virtual buttons to press) was experienced as very natural and easy to use. It was suggested, that there could be similar menu with further functionalities for the right hand as well.

There was some personal variation in preferences and difficulties related to pushing/pressing and pinching or grabbing the objects, but no significant difficulties were reported. Providing multiple options for the user according to preferences should be considered. Using the slide switch for changing the opacity was sometimes experienced as difficult, as well as grabbing the virtual objects.

Some problems in controlling the number of menus also emerged, such as closing, opening and moving the different menus. Many of the issues were seen as matter of learning to use the features. Additionally, it was mentioned that menu and text size is too small, thus it would be good to be able to adjust them.

Other remarks

It should be noted, that one test participant felt simulator sickness symptoms after the test. After the test performance the users were asked if they felt any symptoms. Other users did not have similar symptoms and it was also mentioned, that AR with HoloLens glasses is more comfortable and natural to use than similar kind of VR system. A user described, that with AR system you are not too immersed in digital world, but maintain the sense of real world.

From the safety perspective it was mentioned, that people wear helmets on the construction site. This requirement must be considered when wearing AR glasses.

Further ideas and suggestions

At the end of the interview, the users were asked to give any further ideas and comments for developing and improving the system. The following suggestions emerged:

- In order to compare reality with the plan, it would be good to mark with color where the conflict is. It would be then faster for the analyst to see where the conflict is in the specific space.
- There could be some pre-configuration template or model, in which everything is optimal, so that adjusting opacity etc. would not be needed.
- Colours of the model should match with other plans, projects and so on.
- When there are two persons in different rooms, there could be some possibility for audio communication between the persons.
- System could visualize the location of the person in the building.
- System could provide more options for specific area, such as detailed information on the selected object (e.g. wire, pipe).

3.2. BIM@SiteOffice User Tests

As reported on briefly in Deliverable D3.4 “Prototype System Description and Test Results”, two “in-field” usability tests were conducted to evaluate the BIM@SiteOffice XR Viewer. First, from February 21st to 23rd 2022 at the VIAS Pilot Use Case (PUC) construction site in Madrid, Spain, then from July 19th to 22nd 2022 at the HRS PUC in Lausanne-Bussigny. Both followed roughly the same procedure which is described in detail, below. These usability tests were also reported on in (Aust et

al., 2022, open access: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7198061>). The tests were prepared, instructed and guided by researchers from the University of Stuttgart and Fraunhofer IAQ.

The testing procedure, similarly to the one used for BIM@Construction, consisted of four phases: An introduction, the trial/testing/task phase, questionnaires, and interviews. For the BIM@SiteOffice XR Viewer this procedure was run twice: A single user session to teach and practice the functionalities and interaction techniques and a pair session to apply them.

3.2.1. Use case

The BIM@SiteOffice multi-user-VR-system (aka. XR Viewer) has been described in Deliverables D1.3 (earlier versions), D2.7, D2.8, and D3.1, among others. It offers an immersive 1st person experience of the digital twin of the building via Head Mounted VR Displays (HMD). (There is also a desktop version of the XR Viewer, to be used with a normal PC screen with which users can also join multi-user-VR-sessions. This could be used for the BIM@OffSiteOffice context.) Apart from basic functionality like navigation (flying through the scene with the building models) and showing/hiding the different BIModels, the XR Viewer enables the users to mark different kinds of issues, e.g. sketch safety nets to mark missing safety features, and draw 3D routes via a way-point system.

The usability tests were conducted with 12 test persons overall (6 in Madrid, 6 in Lausanne). These test persons came from different disciplines with a background in the building and construction industry (Site Managers, BIM Managers, Safety Managers, Forepersons). Three of the test participants (TPs 1, 3, and 5 in the listings below) took part in both the BIM@Construction, and the BIM@SiteOffice tests in Lausanne. In both locations (Madrid and Lausanne) the digital twin models (BIModels and Point Clouds from construction site scans) used for the test were from the buildings whose constructions these test persons were working on (the actual PUC constructions).

HTC Vive HMDs were used for the tests (two HTC Vive Pro Eye in Madrid, one HTC Vive Pro Eye and one HTC Vive Pro 2 in Lausanne).

Differences between the Madrid- and the Lausanne-tests

Even though the two in-field tests of the BIM@SiteOffice XR Viewer were conducted following the same procedure and conducted by the same team, there were some slight differences: The tests in Madrid were held in Spanish, whereas the ones in Lausanne were in English and not French. That did create a bit of a language barrier for some test persons, but in all cases colleagues or test supervisors were able to help and translate. In the months between the two tests, the development

of the XR Viewer went on. Changes to the software included an improvement of general stability, slight additions to the Issue Management UI, and the addition of the way-point system.

3.2.2. Method

The following table shows the testing procedure in detail. Both qualitative and quantitative methods were used (see last column of table).

Phase	Description	Goal/Research Question	Method
Day 1			
Intro- duction	Slide presentation about the BIMprove project the testing procedure and the hardware used	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General clarification • Test person consent • Test goals • Testing procedure 	Slide presentation for the whole group of test persons
	Single User	Teach and test interaction techniques	
VR-Intro		Get Test person (TP) familiar with VR devices	Verbal instructions
1st try & reactions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • navigate • explore • model menu handling <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ open/close menu ◦ select/deselect models • issue manipulation menu <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ create issues ◦ edit issues ◦ teleport • laser pointer function 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Get TP to know the functions • Test usability of interaction techniques (How do people get on? Do they remember the techniques intuitively?) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Verbal instructions • Think Aloud (TA), (qualitative) • Observation (by test supervisor, quantitative)
Question- naires	Motion sickness	Is motion sickness a problem?	Summarized Simulator Sickness Questionnaire (1 item)
Interview		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Get general feedback • Would the system help the TP with their work? 	Semi-structured interview
Day 2	Two Users	Test multi-user communication	

VR-Intro	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "Arrive" in VR • Remember interaction techniques 		Verbal instructions
Test tasks	<p>Tasks</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • find each other • explanation and use of laser pointer • model menu handling during and as a means of communication <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ open/close menu ○ select/deselect models • issue manipulation menu as a means of communication <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ create issues ○ edit issues ○ teleport (each other) • laser pointer function as a means of communication 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do TP remember the functions? • Do TP remember the interaction techniques? • What (and how) do TP talk about? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Verbal instructions • Think Aloud (TA), (qualitative) • Concurrent Categorisation of Conversation Topics (see below, qualitative to quantitative) • Observation (by test supervisor, quantitative)
Questionnaires	Motion sickness, Summarized Simulator Sickness Questionnaire (1 item)	Is motion sickness a problem?	Questionnaire (quantitative)
	SUS	Usability testing	Questionnaire (quantitative)
Interview		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Get general feedback • Would the system help the TP with their work? • General user experience and usability of the system • System usefulness • User needs and ideas 	Semi-structured interview

Concurrent Categorisation of Conversation Topics

One of the Methods we used, we called “Concurrent Categorisation of Conversation Topics” (CCCT). This is a method still in development. It has also been reported on in (Aust et al., 2022, open access: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7198061>). The development started during the analyses of the Madrid-tests when we watched back the video and screencast recordings. The method categorises the things testusers talk about in a multi-user setting into pre-defined categories which are graded on a scale. It is a quick and pragmatic heuristic method to estimate the readiness of collaborative multi-user systems. This heuristic scale is based on the notion that the more time users spend communicating about domain problems and possible solutions, instead of talking and worrying about functionalities and interaction techniques of the software, the closer the system is to being “ready for use” in the specific context of use. For the two-user sessions, we rated each point of conversation between the test users on the following scale:

Topic of conversion	Rating	comment	example
Solutions for domain-related issues	9	Construction-related issues, in this case	“We’ll use XY-machine to build this!”
Identification of domain-related issues	7	Construction-related issues, in this case	“What tools will we use to build this?”
Visualisation	5	In this case BIModels or point clouds	“This looks better than in software XY”
Software features	3	Expressions of (new) software requirements.	“I cannot draw, here, can I?”
Interaction techniques	1	Questions on <i>how</i> features can be used.	“How do I mark this as an issue?”
Anything else, relevant	0		
Off-topic / irrelevant	-1		
Silence	-2	(this category was introduced during the tests in Lausanne, and wasn’t there during the analyses of the Madrid tests.)	

Shown below are diagrams of the conversations in each of the three two-user sessions in Madrid. Each pair of dots connected by a horizontal line in depicts the start and end points of a conversation topic.

Figure 4. TPs A and B

Figure 5. TPs C and D

Figure 6. TPs C and D

The next three figures show the diagrams of the conversions of the three two-user sessions in Lausanne. Notice that a category for silence was introduced to make the analyses easier and the diagrams clearer.

Figure 7. TPs 1 and 3

Figure 8. TPs 5 and 7

Figure 9. TPs 6 and 8

These diagrams turn categorized time stamps into a graphical representation of the conversation, that we find helpful in the analyses. One can see how, for example, in the first graph (TPs A and B) after a slow start, the topic of conversation went to the models and concrete construction issues, before requiring an extensive reminder of a specific interaction technique, just after the halftime point of the session. We also see that TPs in general were still busy talking about software features and how they work, or software features they would like, a lot of the time.

3.2.3. Results

System Usability Scale SUS

The SUS scores after the Madrid tests:

Test participant	SUS score
A	95
B	88
C	80
D	83
E	85
F	65

SUS score average Madrid: 83

The SUS scores after the Lausanne-tests:

Test participant	SUS score
1	95
3	80
5	65
6	65
7	73
8	68

SUS score average Lausanne: 74

- Overall SUS score for the BIM@SiteOffice XR Viewer: 79

Based on the SUS scores the usability of the XR Viewer was evaluated as acceptable.

Cybersickness

Cybersickness was measured via a single item questionnaire after each VR session (both single user and pair sessions). The test persons were asked to rate how much they agree or disagree with the statement “I have had or have symptoms such as: general malaise, headache, or nausea” on a 1-5 Likert-scale, where 1 means “strongly disagree” and 5 “strongly agree”. Sickness was not an issue (all scores 2 or below, overall average. 1.3).

Interviews and Observations

The overall feedback of the test persons was very positive and they showed great interest in the system. The observations during the tests and also the interviews support the SUS results that usability is not an issue.

Even though, in the interviews some users praised the overall interaction as “comfortable”, “intuitive and quick”, and “easier to use in comparison with normal BIM”, there are some difficulties with interaction techniques. The XR Viewer seems to have quite a steep learning curve, and a 15 to 20 min single user session does not seem to be enough to remember all the functions and interaction techniques for 24 hours. Some interaction techniques, most prominently the ones of the Issue

Manipulation Mode, take too long and are too cumbersome; some users tried to find work-arounds for not having to use them. The interaction technique for navigation (a kind of point-and-fly technique) seems to lack functionality. TPs missed a function to stand and move on the same level – be at their eye level above the floor and move only laterally with a locked Z-axis.

Especially in the interviews after the Lausanne tests, plenty of ideas for new functionalities came up, here is a selection: Measurement tape, automatic flight (a long way-point routes), drawing, select and grab objects, sections (cut model vertically), “leash” – automatic follow of partner, mini map, clock.

The visualisation in general, especially that of the point clouds received a lot of praise. TPs also thought the way-point system was good idea.

Some test persons also complained about general discomfort caused by the HMD, it was too heavy, too warm, and generally uncomfortable, which makes its use tiring – “in the end I just wanted to get out of VR” was one statement.

Concurrent Categorisation of Conversation Topics CCCT

A look at the CCCT diagrams shows that very little time during the two-users sessions was spent on actual problems or problem solving. We believe, though, that this has more to do with the test setting than with the software or the UI itself. For the test persons the focus was on trying out the system, not on solving problems. They compared the system to what they knew. These tests were not a real working situation for them, where they would try to complete tasks in an efficient way. The conclusion of the CCCT analyses is, that this evaluation method has a lot of potential and is worth to be further developed, but the test setting needs to include more concrete tasks for the test persons to complete cooperatively and efficiently.

3.3. Conclusion

For the final evaluation of BIM@construction, the user tests with actual end-users were organised at the HRS construction site in Lausanne, Switzerland. The system was evaluated as useful for construction work. The most useful and important benefit is BIM@construction’s ability to visualize immediately on site what is built and what was planned to be built. Some improvement suggestions also emerged from the tests.

Similarly, the BIM@SiteOffice user tests have shown that the XR Viewer is a useful tool with acceptable usability, even though there is room for improvement.

4. New BIM detailed UI

For the final development cycle of the BIMprove project, final two “BIM@-Categories” (see 2.3 BIM@Categories) have been chosen to be developed. The final categories are BIM@Emergency and BIM@Anywhere, and are described in the two subsections below.

4.1. BIM@Emergency

BIM@Emergency application for mobile devices is based on the extended Digital Twin concept, where building’s BIM data is combined with 3D model of a construction site (Figure 10) as separate DT layer. Such model can be created via aerial photogrammetry process utilizing images captured by UAV.

Figure 10. BIM data with construction site 3D model.

Additionally, Digital Twin in BIM@Emergency application contains the following new layers: Risks, Warnings, Emergency, and Evacuation pats.

Risks DT layer is used to improve avoidance of emergency situations (Figure 11). For example, areas with flammable materials are marked with “Do not smoke!” sign. Similarly, locations with dangerous equipment are marked as “Do not touch!”.

Figure 11. Risks layer of BIM@Emergency application.

Warnings layer of BIM@Emergency DT is used to mark up areas of construction site where caution is advised: areas near the building are marked with “Wear helmet” sign, and the construction site entrances are marked with “Construction ahead” signs (Figure 12).

Figure 12. Warnings layer of BIM@Emergency application.

Lastly, Emergency layer is used to aid in reaction to emergency situations. This layer is used to show positions of the first aid kits, fire extinguishers, and emergency exit locations (Figure 13). This layer can be combined with Evacuation paths for navigation to emergency exits or gathering spots.

Figure 13. Emergency layer of BIM@Emergency application.

Stripped-down version of BIM@Emergency application can be used with smart watches. For example, when entering risk or warning area, the notification will be shown informing the user of the potential risks. Furthermore, turn-by-turn navigation can be used to guide the user to emergency exit, fire extinguisher, or first aid kit positions (Figure 14).

Figure 14. Smart watch version of BIM@Emergency application.

4.2. BIM@Anywhere

The BIM@Anywhere UI category has been implemented via the BIMprove Web application (aka Web GUI) (<https://cloud.bimprove-h2020.eu/index.html>) that has been described in Deliverables D3.3 "Proof of Concept System Description and Test Results" and D3.4 "Prototype System Description and Test Results", among others. It gives authorised users access to the BIMprove Backend as well as Model and BCF servers. The website was implemented in a responsive way to facilitate accessing it with a wide range of devices and browsers. The following screenshots show some examples:

Figure 15. The main page (project overview), screenshot taken with an iPhone11 in Chrome browser app.

Figure 16. The subpage showing the list of BIMModels of the AFG Gruppen PUC in Oslo (Fyrstikkbakken). Screenshot taken with an iPhone11 in Chrome browser app.

Figure 17. The subpage with the Model Viewer and two of the BIMModels selected and shown (also of the AFG Gruppen PUC in Oslo (Fyrstikkbakken)). Screenshot taken with an iPhone11 in Chrome browser app (landscape mode).

Figure 18. The subpage showing the available issue boards of the VIAS PUC in Madrid. Screenshot taken with an iPadPro in Chrome browser app (landscape mode).

Figure 19. An example BCF-issue page. Screenshot taken with an iPadPro in Chrome browser app (landscape mode).

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Figure 20. The subpage with the Model Viewer of the VIAS PUC in Madrid. Screenshot taken with an iPadPro in Chrome browser app (landscape mode).

Figure 21. Same subpage as above with only the architecture model and one object in focus. Screenshot taken with an iPadPro in Chrome browser app (landscape mode).

5. Final conclusions

Solutions to support the usage of digital twin related to building construction have been developed from several perspectives. Firstly, an alternative approach to categorise BIM users was suggested; instead of having separate user roles, a classification based on usage context is provided. This results in having less BIM@Something solutions, meaning better economy in the UI solutions to be made.

Furthermore, during the updating period of the deliverable 1.3, two BIM user interfaces, namely BIM@Construction and BIM@SiteOffice, were further developed and carefully tested in the real environment which test participants performed several tasks and responded questionnaires. Based on the results, the new UIs were proved useful and the tests provided valuable information for how to improve them.

Two new UI concepts, BIM@Emergency and BIM@AnyWhere, were designed and demonstrated for gathering user feedback.

6. References

- Aust, M., Kvrjic, J-F., Frohnmayer, J., Otto, M., Helin, K. (2021). Multi-User-XR for digital twin data in construction. To be published in: *EuroXR 2021 Application, Exhibition & Demo Track: Proceedings of the Virtual EuroXR Conference*.
- Aust, M., Otto, M., Helin, K. (2020). BIMprove User Interfaces: Multi-User-XR for construction (Poster). In: Helin, K., de Antonio, A., Reyes-Lecuona, A. (Editors): *EuroVR 2020 Application, Exhibition & Demo Track: Proceedings of the Virtual EuroVR Conference*, ISBN 978-951-38-8741-4, 71-75.
- Brooke, J. (1996). "SUS: a 'quick and dirty' usability scale," in *Usability evaluation in industry*. P. W. Jordan, B. Thomas, B.A. Weerdmeester and I. L. McLelland (Eds.) Taylor and Francis Ltd. London, UK.
- Brooke, J. (2013). SUS: A Retrospective. *Journal of Usability Studies*. Vol. 8, Issue 2, February 2013. pp. 29–40.
- Bangor, A., Kortum, P. & Miller, J. (2009). Determining What Individual SUS Scores mean: Adding an Adjective Rating Scale. *Journal of Usability Studies*. Vol. 4, Issue 3, May 2009. pp. 114–123.
- IPQ Presence Questionnaire. *igroup project consortium*, <http://www.igroup.org/projects/ipq/>. accessed autumn 2021.
- Lewis, J. R., & Sauro, J. (2009, July). The factor structure of the system usability scale. In *International conference on human centered design* (pp. 94-103). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.
- Kennedy, R. S., Lane, N. E., Berbaum, K. S., & Lillenthal, M. G. (1993). Simulator sickness questionnaire: An enhanced method for quantifying simulator sickness. *The international journal of aviation psychology*, 3(3), 203-220.

Appendix

Concurrent Categorisation of Conversation Topics

Figure 22. Test persons 1 and 3

Figure 23. Test persons 5 and 7

Figure 24. Test persons 6 and 8